

Use of rose bengal-EDTA system for the generation of electricity in a photogalvanic cell

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Abstract : Rose bengal has been used as a photosensitizer in photogalvanic cell for solar energy conversion. EDTA was used as an electron donor (reductant). The photopotential and photocurrent generated by this cell were found to be 520 mV and 56 μ A, respectively. The effect of various parameters on the electrical output of the cell has been studied. The current voltage (*i-V*) characteristics of the cell has also been observed and a tentative mechanism for the generation of photocurrent in the photogalvanic cell has been proposed. Performance of the cell was determined in dark at its power point.

Keywords : Photogalvanic cell, dye-reductant, Rose Bengal.

The photogalvanic effect was investigated by many workers from time to time¹. Various dye-reductant systems have been used for solar energy conversion but their efficiency and electrical output is relatively low. Therefore, there is an urgent need to search for newer dye-reductant systems with more electrical output and in this context the present work has been undertaken selecting rose bengal as the dye and EDTA as the reductant.

Results and discussion

The effect of the variation of pH on the electrical output of the cell was observed. The effect of pH on the electrical parameters has been studied in the pH range 10.2–11.0 and the results are reported in Table 1.

With increase in pH, there is an increase in the photopotential and photocurrent both, till it reaches a maximum at pH = 10.7. A further increase in the pH resulted in the decrease in the electrical output. The variation of electrical parameters with pH (or NaOH concentration) may be explained on the basis that acid dissociation constant pK_4 of EDTA is 10.95 i.e. at this pH EDTA remains in its completely ionized form and acts as a good donor towards dye molecules. When pH increases from 10.2, number of EDTA molecules in its completely ionized form increases. This increase continues up to pH 10.7. When pH is increased beyond 10.7 there is a decrease in the electrical parameters because more negatively charged species will repel each other and the approach of EDTA molecule to dye molecules is hindered. As a consequence, the electrical output decreases.

Table 1. Effect of pH, dye and reductant concentration

pH	Temp. = 299 K, intensity = 30.0 mW cm ⁻²		Photopotential (mV)	Photocurrent (μ A)
	[RB] $\times 10^4$ M	[EDTA] $\times 10^3$ M		
10.2	2.74	6.94	327.0	62.0
10.4	2.74	6.94	354.0	74.0
10.6	2.74	6.94	625.0	79.0
10.7	2.74	6.94	636.0	82.0
10.8	2.74	6.94	516.0	78.0
10.9	2.74	6.94	460.0	70.0
11.0	2.74	6.94	396.0	64.0
10.7	1.36	6.94	521.0	72.0
10.7	2.74	6.94	636.0	82.0
10.7	4.10	6.94	586.0	74.0
10.7	5.47	6.94	542.0	72.0
10.7	6.84	6.94	492.0	68.0
10.7	2.74	6.36	428.0	58.0
10.7	2.74	6.52	495.0	59.0
10.7	2.74	6.66	575.0	62.0
10.7	2.74	6.80	610.0	68.0
10.7	2.74	6.94	636.0	82.0
10.7	2.74	7.08	502.0	78.0
10.7	2.74	7.22	428.0	74.0

Dependence of photopotential and photocurrent on the concentration of the dye and reductant was also studied and the results are summarized in Table 1. As evident

from the Table 1 that when concentration of dye is lower ($1.36 \times 10^{-4} M$), the photopotential and photocurrent have lower values because few dye molecules are available for excitation and consecutive donation of the electrons to the platinum electrode. When the concentration of dye is increased ($2.74 \times 10^{-4} M$), photopotential and photocurrent increases due to an increase in the number of dye molecules undergoing excitation and electron donation to the electrode. On the other hand, if concentration of dye is further increased, a decrease in photopotential and photocurrent is observed. It is because that only a small fraction of light reaches the dye molecules present near the electrode. Dye molecules present in the bulk of the solution absorb a major portion of the light. Therefore, electron transfer from dye molecules to electrode is retarded, which results in decrease in power output. That is, maximum photocurrent and photopotential is generated at an optimum value of dye concentration.

An optimum value for reductant concentration was observed at which maximum power was generated ($6.94 \times 10^{-3} M$) and with decrease in reductant concentration, a fall in power output has been observed, as very few reductant molecule are available for electron donation to the dye molecules. On the other hand, higher concentration of reductant causes hindrance to dye molecules to approach the electrode in the desired time limit. Thus higher concentration of reductant also results in decrease in power output of cell.

The photocurrent showed a linear increasing behaviour with an increase in the intensity of light whereas the photopotential increases in an exponential manner (Table 2). The number of photons per unit area, (incident power), striking the dye molecules around the platinum electrode, increase with the increase in the light intensity and there is a rise in photopotential and photocurrent. However, an increase in light intensity will also raise the temperature of the cell. Intensity of 30 mW cm^{-2} was used for

Table 2. Effect of light intensity

[RB] = $2.74 \times 10^{-4} M$, [EDTA] = $6.94 \times 10^{-3} M$, pH = 10.7, Temp. = 299 K

Light intensity (mW cm^{-2})	Photocurrent (μA)	Photopotential (mV)	log V
10.0	66.0	551.0	2.7405
15.0	72.0	578.0	2.7619
20.0	74.0	596.0	2.7752
25.0	78.0	617.0	2.7903
30.0	82.0	636.0	2.8035
35.0	86.0	647.0	2.8109

investigation.

The effect of variation of diffusion length on the current parameters (i_{max} , i_{eq} and the rate of initial generation of current) was studied using H-cells of different dimensions. The results are given in Table 3. There is a sharp increase in photocurrent in first few minutes of illumination and then there is a gradual decrease to a final value of photocurrent indicates a slow rate determining step after a rapid reaction, which is responsible for the generation of current. The observation of the effect of diffusion length on current parameters were used to know more about the electrode active species donating an electron to the electrode or accepting an electron from the electrode, various processes may be considered for photocurrent generation.

There are three possibilities for the combination of electroactive species :

- Active species in illuminated chamber may be the dye (D) itself and the oxidized form of the reductant (R^+) is active in the dark chamber.
- The leuco (D_L) or semi-leuco (D_S) form of the dye and the oxidized form of the reductant (R^+) are the electroactive species in illuminated and dark chambers, respectively.
- The dye (D) itself is electrode active species in dark chamber and its leuco (D_L) or semi-leuco (D_S) form in the illuminated chamber.

Table 3. Variation of diffusion length

[RB] = $2.94 \times 10^{-4} M$, [EDTA] = $6.94 \times 10^{-3} M$, pH = 10.7, intensity = 30 mW cm^{-2}

Diffusion length (cm)	Maximum photocurrent (i_{max}) (μA)	Equilibrium photocurrent (i_{eq}) (μA)	Rate of initial generation of current ($\mu\text{A min}^{-1}$)
1.0	48.0	46.0	0.01047
1.5	47.0	45.0	0.01135
2.0	50.0	42.0	0.01262
2.5	52.0	40.0	0.01354
3.0	56.0	38.0	0.01555

The open circuit voltage (V_{oc}) and short circuit current (i_{sc}) of the photogalvanic cell were measured from a digital multimeter (keeping the circuit open) and from a microammeter (keeping the circuit closed), respectively. The current and potential values in between these two extreme value (V_{oc} and i_{sc}) were recorded with the help of the carbon pot (linear 470 K) connected in the circuit of the multimeter, through which an external load was

Note

applied. The i - V curve of the cell deviated from its ideal regular rectangular shape. The value of potential and current at power point is represented as V_{pp} and i_{pp} , respectively. With the help of the i - V curve, the fill factor and conversion efficiency of the cell were determined as 0.36 and 0.9706%, respectively, using the formula,

$$\text{Fill factor} = \frac{V_{pp} \times i_{pp}}{V_{oc} \times i_{oc}}$$

$$\text{Conversion efficiency} = \frac{V_{pp} \times i_{pp}}{\text{Intensity}} \times 100\%$$

The performance of the cell was studied by applying the external load necessary to have current and potential at power point after removing the source of light. It was observed that the cell can be used in the dark at its power point for 28 min. The photovoltaic cell cannot be used in the dark even for a second, whereas, the photogalvanic system has an additional advantage of being used in the dark, of course, with lower conversion efficiency.

Mechanism of photocurrent generation is similar to other cases done from our laboratory¹.

Experimental

Rose Bengal (Chroma), EDTA (Ranbaxy) and sodium hydroxide (IDPL) were used. All the solutions were

prepared in doubly distilled water and kept in amber coloured containers to protect from light. A mixture of solutions of dye, EDTA, NaOH and water was filled in the H-shaped glass cell. Platinum electrode ($1 \times 1 \text{ cm}^2$) was dipped in one limb of the cell and saturated calomel electrode (SCE) in the other. The platinum electrode was exposed to a 200 W tungsten lamp (Philips) and the limb containing SCE was kept in the dark. A water filter was used to avoid thermal effects. The photopotential and photocurrent generated; by the system rose bengal/EDTA/ $\text{OH}^-/h\nu$ were measured by a digital conductance multimeter (CIE 5605) and microammeter (Kew), respectively. The current-voltage (i - V) characteristics of the cell were studied by using an external load (linear 470 K) in the circuit.

References

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